

Applying branch-and-bound and petri net methods in solving the two-sided assembly line balancing problem

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Abstract : This paper combines the branch-and-bound method and the petri net to solve the two-sided assembly line balancing problem, thus facilitating effective branching and pruning of tasks. By integrating features of the petri net, such as reachability graph and incidence matrix, the propose method can support the branch-and-bound to effectively reduce poor branches with systematic graphs. Test results suggest that using petri net in the branching process can effectively guide the system trigger process, and thus, lead to consistent results.

Keywords : Two-sided assembly line balancing problem, Petri net, Branch-and-bound method

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